

THE EFFECTS OF MOISTURE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER PAPER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS/POLYAMIDE 6

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Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) has been widely used in different fields including aerospace, civil engineering, automotive, sports goods, etc. Different matrices can be used such as polyamide (PA), polypropylene (PP), polycarbonate (PC). In the actual application process, considering the cost control and the cohesiveness between carbon fibers and matrix, PA6 is expected to be applicable for mass-production application. However, environment factors, such as temperature, water absorption and so on, will have negative effects on the service life of PA6 products. The usability and security will decline, which will restrict the wide application of CFRTP and thereby indirectly increase the energy consumption. Therefore, in this research, the water diffusion process in CPT/PA6 specimens was studied. The effects of water absorption and temperature on CPT/PA6 material were analysed. The flexural properties of CPT/PA6 material were estimated.

Water absorption test

- The water absorption test was conducted at 70°C to accelerate this process, which is higher than the glass transition temperature.
- Fick's diffusion law was used to analyze the water absorption mechanism of CPT/PA6 material.
- The diffusion coefficient of water in specimen D can be calculated by equation (1).

$$D = \frac{\pi h^2}{16} \left(\frac{k}{W_\infty} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1: The water absorption of CPT/PA6

Fig. 2: Weight gain of CPT material with Fick's diffusion model

	$k (\times 10^{-3} h^{-1})$	$h (\times 10^{-3} m)$	$W_\infty (\%)$	$D (\times 10^{-8} m^2 \cdot h^{-1})$
Sample 1	8.58	3.00	5.77	3.91
Sample 2	8.55	3.01	5.75	3.93
Sample 3	8.39	3.06	5.73	3.95
Sample 4	8.65	3.05	5.88	3.95
Sample 5	8.70	3.04	5.88	3.97
Ave. Value	/	/	5.80	3.94

Table 1: Results of water absorption test.

Three-point bending test

- Effects of water contents on flexural properties of CPT material.

Fig. 3: Stress-strain curves of CPT material in different water contents

State of specimens	Flexural strength (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Standard deviation (GPa)
Dry	407.3	8.955	18.04	0.2684
Half water absorbed	243.3	3.587	11.82	0.1227
Saturated	240.4	6.642	11.93	0.3262

Table 2: Flexural properties of CPT material in different water contents

- Effects of temperature on flexural properties of CPT material.

Fig. 4: Stress-strain curves of CPT material in different temperatures

Temperature	Flexural strength (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Standard deviation (GPa)
-25°C	428.7	9.420	18.64	0.1606
25°C	407.3	8.954	18.04	0.2685
75°C	307.7	4.629	14.65	0.3107
100°C	259.9	8.779	12.75	0.1281

Table 3: Flexural properties of CPT material in different temperatures

Conclusions

- The water absorption process of CPT/PA6 material was observed. The kinetics of water diffusion was analyzed, which is proved to conform to Fick's diffusion law.
- When the weight gain ratio is the same, the flexural properties of specimens with low water content declined more than those with high water contents.
- The flexural properties of CPT/PA6 material decrease as temperature increases, and the ratio decreases more at high temperature than at low temperature.